

D5.5: Report on operations for selection of host country for EMPHASIS central hub and potential services

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Documents used in the preparation of this deliverable:

- European Commission. "Council Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 of 25 June 2009 on the Community Legal Framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)," 2009
- European Commission, "Legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium - ERIC: Practical Guidelines
- EMPHASIS-PREP Deliverable 5.1: Scenarios for governance structures
- EMPHASIS-PREP Deliverable 5.3: Options to form a legal entity
- EMPHASIS-PREP Deliverable 5.4: Governance framework including roles and responsibilities for the implementation phase
- EMPHASIS-PREP Deliverable 5.6: Governance and Statutes for the EMPHASIS Operational Phase

Executive Summary

As part of its progress towards an ERIC (as confirmed by the EMPHASIS Interim General Assembly (IGA) at the 4th IGA meeting, March-2021) and in order to fulfil its aims and objectives as a fully realised pan-European research infrastructure (RI), EMPHASIS will require the selection of a host country / statutory seat.

This report proposes a process for the selection (including assessment) of the host country for EMPHASIS central hub and potential services. The proposed selection process detailed in this report is not final and will require ratification by the EMPHASIS IGA (or its successor) once agreement on the EMPHASIS Operational Phase strategic direction has been agreed.

1. Expectations, responsibilities, and requirements

1.1. Expectations and responsibilities

The country that will register the EMPHASIS ERIC, the statutory seat country will also be responsible for the administration of EMPHASIS-ERIC, this will involve supporting the EMPHASIS Directorate and Director General as per the following:

- The EMPHASIS Directorate shall be the executive body of EMPHASIS ERIC. It shall be composed of the Director-General, who shall be the legal representative of EMPHASIS ERIC, the Director-General will represent EMPHASIS ERIC and promote the research infrastructure at the national and international level.
- The EMPHASIS General Assembly / Board shall appoint and dismiss the Director-General.
- The Director-General shall take decisions affecting the overall infrastructure, in line with the EMPHASIS Strategic Plan as approved by the EMPHASIS General Assembly / Board
- The EMPHASIS Directorate shall carry out the day-to-day management of EMPHASIS ERIC and shall be responsible for the implementation of the decisions by the EMPHASIS General Assembly / Board, including but not limited to:
 - Preparation and execution of the EMPHASIS Strategic Plan, for which it will seek the advice of the EMPHASIS National Node representative and the EMPHASIS Advisory Board(s)
 - Preparation and execution the EMPHASIS Financial Plan including proposing a yearly budget showing detailed estimates of the projected income and expenditure of EMPHASIS ERIC for the following financial year, and preparation of the annual financial accounts of EMPHASIS ERIC
 - Preparing and negotiating service level agreements with EMPHASIS National Nodes;
 - Attending the meetings of the EMPHASIS General Assembly / Board in a non-voting capacity
 - Preparing the agenda for the EMPHASIS General Assembly / Board meetings and prepare the deliberations of the EMPHASIS General Assembly / Board
 - Informing the EMPHASIS General Assembly / Board about all relevant matters related to EMPHASIS that would either require a decision or acknowledgement
 - Managing, appointing and dismissing the EMPHASIS Central Office staff
 - Preparing the annual activity report for the European Commission

1.2. Requirements

As per the decision of the EMPHASIS IGA, EMPHASIS will be established as an ERIC, there are only two formal requirements that need to be fulfilled by the hosting country of the ERIC's statutory seat.

Article 8 of the Council Regulation (EC) no 723/2009 stipulates that an ERIC:

*"Shall be located on the territory of a member which shall be a Member State or an associated country."*¹

The ERIC Practical Guidelines further elaborate upon this article by stating that the statutory seat:

*"Should be located in a place (address) where some or all of the activities [of the ERIC] are carried out. It is not sufficient to have a mailbox in a country where no actual operations are carried out."*²

Subject to approval by the EMPHASIS IGA, it is also proposed that further criteria may need to be applied when selecting the EMPHASIS host country to ensure effective and efficient operation and leadership:

- The hosting country should have sufficient capacity available to fulfil the requirements of hosting an ERIC
- The hosting country should demonstrate the support of the other EMPHASIS member countries
- The hosting country should demonstrate strong commitment to the establishment and long-term operation of the ERIC

¹ European Commission. "Council Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 of 25 June 2009 on the Community Legal Framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)," 2009, available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32009R0723>.

² European Commission, "Legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium - ERIC: Practical Guidelines," available at https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/pdf/eric_en.pdf.

2. Summary of the process

Call for applications

- Interested parties submit an Expression of interest (Eoi) to the EMPHASIS IGA providing:
 - High level detail of plans for EMPHASIS Host Country / Statutory seat
 - Relevant expertise in progressing RIs through the ERIC application process
 - Commitments / letters of support from relevant national stakeholders such as government departments and national funders

Eligibility checks

- EMPHASIS interim support and coordination office review Eoi applications as per the defined eligibility criteria (see Section 4 for further information)

Review and assessment

- Post-check, Eois are presented to an independent international panel of experts (with wide ranging expertise) for review, the panel will provide a recommendation to the EMPHASIS IGA on a preferred applicant
- EMPHASIS IGA review the independent panel assessment and ratify the recommendation

(Optional) Full proposal

- Dependent of the number of Eoi applications, a more detailed assessment of the proposals may be required in which case after an initial assessment a selected number of applicants may be invited to submit more detailed Full proposal (see Section 5 for further information)

3. Expression of interest (Eol)

EMPHASIS partners interested in becoming the EMPHASIS Operational Phase Host Country will be invited to prepare and submit an Eol to EMPHASIS interim support and coordination Office. This Eol presents the initial step in the decision on EMPHASIS' statutory seat. As part of this process, applicants may be expected to provide details on the following:

- Applicant (contact details), hosting institution / entity
- Administrative competencies (international project management, legal, financial)
- Scientific commitment (e.g. summary of national investment / subject prioritisation)
- Letter of Support from:
 - Hosting institution / entity
 - National representing entity in the EMPHASIS IGA
 - National Funder(s) if not already covered by previous points

Details and decision of the administration of an Eol proposal should be defined as part of the related Implementation Phase activities.

4. Eligibility criteria options

A critical part of the EMPHASIS Host Country selection process is the defining of eligible applicants below presents options for eligibility to be decided as part of the ongoing engagements with the EMPHASIS IGA.

4.1. Options for country status eligibility

Eligibility	Positives	Concerns
Open (member state / associated country)	Widen potential pool of applicants - increasing competition	Decrease the commitment levels of application / less understanding of EMPHASIS progress to date
IGA member	Application likely come from an existing EMPHASIS partner, ensuring continuity of strategy and greater	Slightly reduced pool of potential applicants

	understanding of the project while still opening up to diverse applicant pool	
Commitment to join EMPHASIS-ERIC	Participation in EMPHASIS project is guaranteed, applicants will have full understanding of EMPHASIS objectives and challenges, and likely experience of joint European research initiatives	Heavily reduced pool of potential applicants, reduction in diversity of applicant / separation of EMPHASIS from existing initiatives

4.2. Further eligibility criteria

- The submission of the EoI is supported by the respective national stakeholders / members of the EMPHASIS IGA in the form of a ‘Letter of Support’ signed and submitted by the representing entity
- The application demonstrates recent (within 5 years) national investment in or national strategic prioritisation of plant and crop phenotyping with a commitment to investment
- The applicant can demonstrate relevant expertise in progressing RIs through the ERIC application process
- The applicant can demonstrate the dialogue with funders for the participation in EMPHASIS-ERIC

Eligibility criteria will be finalised once agreement on the EMPHASIS Operational Phase strategic direction has been agreed during the EMPHASIS Implementation Phase as part of the ongoing engagement with the EMPHASIS IGA.

5. Review and assessment

5.1. Independent evaluation

The statutory seat will form a critical component in the mature EMPHASIS RI and thus the decision on host country is of vital strategic importance, as it will have a considerable impact upon the success and efficiency of EMPHASIS ERIC. Given this importance, it is paramount that a robust and transparent decision-making process focused on a common and collaborative approach is founded. Assessment of the proposals will be undertaken by an international panel of experts with experience of the following: ESFRI, innovation and research organisations, Research Infrastructure

administration, industry and commerce, policymaking and/or civil society. The panel will assess the applications against the assessment criteria, its responsibilities include:

- Advising the EMPHASIS IGA issues relating / that may impact the success of the EMPHASIS Host Country
- Supporting the EMPHASIS IGA Host Country decision making process in an open, transparent, and objective manner
- Providing a recommendation for the EMPHASIS IGA on Host Country proposals (final decisions will be subject to ratification by the EMPHASIS IGA)

5.2. Ratification by EMPHASIS IGA

Post assessment by the international panel of experts the chair of the group will present their recommendations to the EMPHASIS IGA. Based on these recommendations the IGA will then decide on the host country for EMPHASIS central hub and potential services.

6. (Optional) Full proposal

Demand management dependent, there may be a requirement for a second round of proposal assessment. If there is a large number of EoI applications the EMPHASIS IGA may wish to invite two to three proposals for a “Full proposal” application. This would be more developed, detailed and more defined than EoI proposal with the information requirement being greater and reflective of the important nature of the decision.

There are two options for this demand management that will need to be decided in consultation with the EMPHASIS IGA:

Option 1 - IGA demand management	Option 2 - Panel demand management
<p>The IGA would consider the initial EoI proposals and decide internally on which to invite to submit full proposals</p> <p>Pros</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased time / administrative efficiency <p>Concerns</p>	<p>The international panel of experts would consider the initial EoI proposals recommend two or three proposals for full submission - this would then be confirmed by the IGA</p> <p>Pros</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greater level of neutrality to the assessment process <p>Concerns</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Impartiality / conflicts of interest may be difficult to manage	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Increased administrative burden and time cost for all parties involved
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As part of this stage it may also be preferable to provide additional reviews of the proposal to aid the international panel of experts in their assessment.

Details and decision of the administration of a full proposal should be defined as part of the related Implementation Phase activities.

Annex 1: Check list

Deliverable Check list (to be checked by the “Deliverable leader”)

	Check list	Comments
Before	I have checked the due date and have planned completion in due time	<i>Please inform Management Team of any foreseen delays</i>
	The title corresponds to the title in the DOW	<i>If not please inform the Management Team with justification</i>
	The dissemination level corresponds to that indicated in the DOW	
	The contributors (authors) correspond to those indicated in the DOW	
	The Table of Contents has been validated with the Activity Leader	<i>Please validate the Table of Content with your Activity Leader before drafting the deliverable</i>
	I am using the EMPHASIS deliverable template (title page, styles etc.)	<i>Available in “New EMPHASIS Logo, Templates, CI” on the collaborative workspace</i>
The draft is ready		
After	I have written a good summary at the beginning of the Deliverable	<i>A 1-2 pages max. summary is mandatory (not formal but really informative on the content of the Deliverable)</i>
	The deliverable has been reviewed by all contributors (authors)	<i>Make sure all contributors have reviewed and approved the final version of the deliverable. You should leave sufficient time for this validation.</i>
	I have done a spell check and verified the English	
	I have sent the final version to the WP Leader and to the Project coordinator (cc to the project manager) for approval	<i>Send the final draft to your WPLLeader and the coordinator with cc to the project manager on the 1st day of the due month and leave 2 weeks for feedback. Inform the reviewer of the changes (if any) you have made to address their comments. Once validated by the 2 reviewers and the coordinator, send the final version to the Project Manager who will then submit it to the EC.</i>